

Numerical Procedure for the Estimation of the Aeroelastic Divergence Limit of a Composite Aircraft Wing using Higher Order Aerodynamics

Kafkas Angelos

Laboratory of Technology & Strength of Materials, Dept. of Mechanical Engineering & Aeronautics, University of Patras, PanepistimioupolisRion, 26500 Patras, Greece

angel.kafkas@upnet.gr

Lampeas George

Laboratory of Technology & Strength of Materials, Dept. of Mechanical Engineering & Aeronautics, University of Patras, PanepistimioupolisRion, 26500 Patras, Greece

labeas@mech.upatras.gr

**corresponding author:*

Kafkas Angelos (angel.kafkas@upnet.gr)

Abstract

The usage of implicit coupled schemes combining high fidelity aerodynamics and structural mechanics codes in studying static aeroelastic phenomena bears the promise of successfully obtaining static aeroelastic solutions to a wide range of technological fluid-structure interaction problems regardless of the type of geometry, aerodynamic and structural non-linearities (such as those that can be met in advanced composite wing structures). Virtually any structure operating in the presence of fluid can be handled provided the necessary computational resources are available.

This promise however is intertwined with significant challenges. The results from a coupled analysis using high fidelity aerodynamics are obtained in an unintuitive form. Although the detailed flow and structural response is calculated, using these results to determine the divergence limit can be problematic.

An important challenge arises from the inability of the cfd mesh updating and deforming algorithms to successfully handle the very large deformations close to the divergence limit. This leads to the need that the divergence limit be estimated by the closest successful coupled solutions to it in terms of velocity.

Furthermore the time and associated computational cost for each coupled solution renders a high number of solutions at different velocity values highly impractical.

In the scope of the present work a procedure to obtain the divergence limit and an estimation of the numerical uncertainty of this calculation is presented, with the aim of bypassing or mitigating the aforementioned issues.

Given a pre-defined velocity range in which the divergence limit is to be studied, this procedure relies on successive estimations of the divergence velocity based on a Taylor series expansion. The estimations are built around coupled static aeroelastic solutions at successive velocity points. A way to efficiently modify the velocity point spacing during the procedure to reduce the number of required solutions and consequently the computational cost is also studied.

The numerical procedure mentioned above will be applied to the calculation of the divergence limit of a two dimensional airfoil and a high aspect ratio regional airliner composite wing to prove validity of usage in complex static aeroelastic problems.

The presented work has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program, GREen TurboProp Experimental Laminar Flow Wind Tunnel Testing (GRETEL) project, under Grant Agreement no. 737671

Estimation of the Aeroelastic Divergence Limit of a Composite Aircraft Wing using Higher Order Aerodynamics

Angelos Kafkas
MSc Eng.

Lampeas George
Professor

- Scope
- Procedure in 2D problems
- Effective marching scheme
- Coupling Issues
- Generalization for 3d problems
- Important considerations
- Proposals for further work

Solving for divergence using high order aerodynamics

➤ Promise

- ❖ Higher fidelity of results
- ❖ Suitable for wings with non-linear aerodynamics
- ❖ Suitable for virtually any shape (aeronautical or other)

➤ Issues

- ❖ Mesh deformation issues/ deterioration of mesh quality near divergence
- ❖ Stall, drag divergence might take place before mathematical divergence

Need to judge divergence limit from solutions before actual divergence

➤ Divergence detected when:

- ❖ 2 successive velocity estimations converge
- ❖ The derivative $dV_{d,est}/da_\epsilon$ between the prediction values at Δa_ϵ and $2\Delta a_\epsilon$ from same solution point tends to converge to zero

Successive estimations of the velocity using Taylor Theorem:

$$V_{d,est} = V_1 + \left. \frac{dV}{da_\epsilon} \right|_1 (\Delta a_\epsilon)$$

➤ Divergence

- ❖ Infinite change in twist angle for small changes in velocity
- ❖ *The velocity predictions from successive estimations tend to converge*

❖ The slope of velocity as a function of the twist angle is evaluated using a backward difference scheme:

$$\left. \frac{dV}{da_\epsilon} \right|_1 = \frac{(V_1 - V_0)}{(a_{\epsilon 1} - a_{\epsilon 0})}$$

❖ Termination criteria

$$e_{V_{d21}} = \left| \frac{(V_{d,est2} - V_{d,est1})}{V_{d,est1}} \right| < \text{end_crit}$$

$$e_{V_{d\Delta\alpha}} = \left| \frac{(V_{d,est@\Delta a} - V_{d,est@2\Delta a})}{\Delta a} \right| < \text{end_crit}$$

CFD flow data	
Flow equations	Inviscid compressible (3d Euler)
Density correction	Ideal gas
Solver type	PISO with skewness correction

Geometrical data	
Chord length	1 m
Wingspan	1 m
Incidence Angle	1°

Important aeroelastic parameters		
Distance of aerodynamic centre from centre of gravity	r_{ac}	$-2.183 \cdot 10^{-1}m$
Distance of elastic axis from centre of gravity	r_{ea}	$2.089 \cdot 10^{-1}m$
Torsional axis constant	K_a	$1310 Nm/^\circ$

Coupled Solution Results	
Freestream velocity (m/sec)	Aeroelastic twist (deg)
25	1,37E-02
50	5,72E-02
75	1,37E-01
100	2,91E-01
125	5,34E-01
150	1,08E+00
175	2,21E+00
185	3,84E+00
195	9,03E+00
197	1,13E+01

Procedure in 2D Problems

Compressibility and aerodynamic centre modification taken into account

Vd Estimation		
Divergence velocity estimation	$e_{V_{d12}}$	$e_{V_{d,\Delta\alpha}}$
6,52E+03		
3,59E+03	4,49E-01	1,00E+00
1,89E+03	4,73E-01	5,48E-01
1,23E+03	3,48E-01	2,83E-01
6,21E+02	4,97E-01	1,79E-01
3,77E+02	3,92E-01	8,00E-02
2,31E+02	3,88E-01	3,86E-02
1,99E+02	1,36E-01	1,07E-02
1,97E+02	1,23E-02	3,36E-03

Difference with theory

Estimated Vd	199 m/sec
Difference to theoretical Vd	6.66%
Difference to corrected theoretical Vd	3.98%

➤ Coupled solutions marching scheme considerations

- ❖ Small number of complete coupled solutions feasible
- ❖ Equidistance marching can be problematic

➤ Modified Procedure

- ❖ Initially two divergence free velocity points are solved
- ❖ Each next point is estimated from the previous one using a Taylor approximation
- ❖ In the event of mesh deterioration (divergence overshoot) then the velocity increment is bisected to obtain the next solution point

Modified marching procedure for airfoil problem with $\lambda=0.85$

$$V_{next} = V_{solu\ point} + \lambda \cdot \frac{dV}{da_{\epsilon}} \cdot (a_{\epsilon, solu\ point+1} - a_{\epsilon, solu\ point})$$

relaxation factor

- CFD mesh deformation and load transfer issues in coupling steady state Structural and CFD solution
 - ❖ Steady state solution for structure might lead to large amplitude deformations
 - CFD mesh updating/deforming algorithms designed for small amplitudes of motion per iteration
 - Relaxation factors and subiterations must be employed
 - Increasing velocity rapidly increases the deformation increment per iteration to the structure for the same total number of iterations and relaxation factors

- Mitigation Strategy
 - ❖ Solve the coupled problem for the initial velocity point
 - starting from few subiterations and no relaxation
 - tweaking the values until CFD mesh quality is sufficiently preserved
 - Obtain the minimum increment of deformation passed to the structure for the first solution in which the mesh quality is adequately preserved
 - ❖ For the analysis of the next velocity points
 - run only a few n iterations,
 - stop and tweak relaxation and subiterations until the increment of deformation per iteration is comparable to the initial velocity point's successful solution
 - Restart the analysis with those values

➤ Generalization

- ❖ The total deformation tends to exponentially increase near divergence (equilibrium cannot be reached)
- ❖ The numerical procedure generalized to 3d, total deformation instead of twist angle monitored
- ❖ Also possible to monitor total strain to determine the velocity at structural failure point

Successive estimations using Taylor Theorem and total strain increment:

$$M_{d,est} = M_1 + \left. \frac{dM}{d\varepsilon_{tot}} \right|_1 (\Delta\varepsilon_{tot})$$

, where $\Delta\varepsilon_{tot}$ the distance from solution point to max strain limit

Successive estimations using Taylor Theorem and total deformation increment:

$$M_{d,est} = M_1 + \left. \frac{dM}{du_{tot}} \right|_1 (\Delta u_{tot})$$

➤ Termination Criteria

$$e_{M_{d21}} = \left| \frac{(M_{d,est2} - M_{d,est1})}{M_{d,est1}} \right| < \text{end_crit}$$

$$e_{M_{d\Delta u}} = \left| \frac{(M_{d,est@\Delta u} - M_{d,est@2\Delta u})}{\Delta u} \right| < \text{end_crit}$$

➤ Two composite high aspect ratio regional airliner wings

- ❖ Same material (carbon fibre quasi-isotropic fabric), same wingspan, incidence and dihedral angles
- ❖ Different sweep angle -18 and 18 degrees

Wing operating conditions

$\rho_{static} \left(\frac{kg}{m^3} \right)$	0.416
P_{static} (KPa)	30
T_{static} (K)	230
Design max cruise Mach	0.6

Wing geometry

Root chord c (m)	0.416
Tapper ratio λ	0.4
Incidence angle (deg)	2-0
Dihedral d (deg)	3-5
Sweep angle (deg)	-18,18
Airfoil	NACA63210

Generalization for 3d problems

Drag divergence limit, lift reduced

M_{dest}	e_{Md}	$e_{Md,\Delta u}$
5,68E-01		2,12E-01
7,41E-01	3,05E-01	5,97E-01
6,91E-01	6,74E-02	2,84E-01
7,44E-01	7,71E-02	2,69E-01
8,18E-01	9,96E-02	2,91E-01
1,01E+00	2,34E-01	6,55E-01
8,07E-01	2,00E-01	1,03E-01

Divergence not detected!

Due to favourable bending-torsion coupling, divergence is delayed enough for the drag divergence limit to be reached first

$M_{d,est}$	e_{Md}	$e_{Md,\Delta u}$
6,63E-01		1,25E-01
6,21E-01	6,25E-02	3,56E-02
6,31E-01	1,47E-02	2,34E-02
6,59E-01	4,49E-02	2,29E-02
6,66E-01	1,10E-02	2,00E-02
6,69E-01	3,83E-03	1,66E-02
6,73E-01	5,91E-03	1,35E-02
6,78E-01	7,84E-03	1,07E-02

← Estimated Divergence limit

- Due to high fidelity solution most flow effects are included
 - ❖ Other problems might occur before actual divergence
 - Stall
 - Drag divergence and shockwave formation
 - ❖ Solution must be monitored on both sides (structural/fluid) to determine such scenarios
 - Abrupt reduction in lift and total deformation provides warning
 - The last velocity increment is spitted as needed to clarify whether divergence or other critical issues mentioned above take place first

Further work

- Application of the divergence estimation procedure to more wing geometries and comparison with bibliography
- Application of the procedure to non-aeronautical shapes
- Usage in novel divergence critical wing concepts like ultra high aspect ratio or forward swept wings

Thank you for paying attention!

Questions?

This work was supported by H2020 JTI-CS2-2016-
CFP03-REG-01-02 GREen Turboprop Experimental
Laminar Flow Wind Tunnel Testing (GRETEL)
Programme grant agreement No 737671